

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS OF MOWRAH FLOWERS
(*B. LATIFOLIA*). PART II. VITAMINS, ENZYMES
AND MISCELLANEOUS ANALYSES AND
EFFECT OF STORAGE

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(Received August 17, 1954)

Patel¹ found mowrah flowers to contain thiamin, niacin, pantothenic acid, biotin and inositol by microbiological method. Joshi and Magar² reported 56 mg. % of vitamin-C in the dried flowers. The authors have estimated from the mowrah flowers ascorbic acid, thiamin, riboflavin and niacin chemically, and folic acid microbiologically.

Fowler *et al.*³ have shown the presence of maltase, catalase, emulsin, amylase and oxidase. The present authors have determined only one enzyme, ascorbic acid oxidase, on account of rapid and gradual decrease in vitamin-C content in the flowers on storage. After one month's storage, the vitamin-C content was found to be negligible.

In the miscellaneous analysis, acidity (and p_H), organic acids, betaine, pigments and tannins were determined. Betaine content was looked for as there was a difference in total nitrogen and amino-acid nitrogen contents. As the extract of flowers was highly coloured, the presence of water-soluble pigments (anthocyanins) was also investigated. Fowler *et al.*³ simply detected the presence of tannins. Here, the estimation was carried out to determine its percentage.

As mowrah flowers are gathered and stored by hill-tribes and villagers of Northern part and other parts of India, it is necessary to ascertain the retention of the various nutrients of these flowers when stored. So this work was undertaken to study the composition of stored mowrah flowers. These flowers, as soon as received, were therefore kept for storage for one year at 10°, 28°-30° (room temp.), 37° and 43° and the changes noted periodically.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Vitamins.—Vitamin-C was determined according to the method of Robinson and Stotz⁴ with 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol. Thiamin was estimated by converting it into thiochrome according to the method of Harris and Wang⁵ with some modifications. Riboflavin was determined by a fluorometric method of Scott *et al.*⁶ with a little modification. For niacin, the method of Sweeney⁷ was followed. Folic acid was assayed by a microbiological technique after Teply and Elvehjem⁸.

The vitamins were assayed from the fresh mowrah flowers (Table I).

TABLE I

Vitamins.	Amount per 100 g. of flowers	
	on fresh wt. basis.	on dry wt. basis.
Ascorbic acid	29 mg.	36.99 mg.
Thiamin	110 µg.	140.3 µg.
Riboflavin	660	841.8
Niacin	1.413 mg.	1.802 mg.
Folic acid	167.8	214

Enzyme.—For ascorbic acid oxidase, the method of Birch, Harris and Ray⁹ with minor modifications was followed. Buffer of p_H 5.6 was prepared from 0.02M oxalic acid and 0.02M-NaOH solutions as suggested by Dhopeslhwarkar and Magar¹⁰.

After one month's storage, vitamin-C content dropped from 36.99 mg. to 4.6 mg. per 100 g. It showed that vitamin-C was somehow destroyed or changed to some of the products. This destruction led to the investigation of ascorbic acid oxidase which was found to be present (Table II).

TABLE II

Destruction of vitamin-C due to ascorbic acid oxidase.

No.	Time.	Solution mixture.	Titre.	Amount vit. C.	Loss of vit. C.	Loss of vit. C.
1	Blank	1 ml substrate + 1 ml. water + 2 ml. oxalic acid	5.00 ml.	200 µg	...	...
2	0 min.	2 ml. solution + 2 ml. oxalic acid	4.20	168	30 µg.	...
3	5	Do	3.90	156	44	12 µg.
4	15	Do	3.30	132	68	36
5	25	Do	2.75	110	90	58
6	35	Do	2.30	93	107	75

The destruction of vitamin-C by ascorbic acid oxidase (from the mowrah flower extract) is not a linear function. The activity of ascorbic acid oxidase decreases with the increase in time intervals.

Miscellaneous.—Acidity was determined by the method of Miller¹¹ and expressed as per cent citric acid (w/w). p_H of 10% mowrah extract was determined by testing with different indicators. Simultaneous determinations of malic and succinic acids were carried out according to the method of Guinn Barr¹². A colorimetric method of Bendelin¹³ was applied for the estimation of betaine. Tannins were determined by the usual A.O.A.C. method. Estimation of crude pigments was carried out according to Sondheimer and Kertesz's method¹⁴.

The analytical data are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

			Percentage (on dry wt. basis).
Acidity	...	...	1.802 (as citric acid)
Succinic acid	...	...	1.462
Betaine	...	...	1.089
Malic acid	...	...	1.181
Crude pigments	...	...	0.2572 (as anthocyanins)
Tannins	...	...	1.325 (as gallic-tannic acid)
pH of the 10% extract	...	...	4.0-4.5

Storage experiments.—The fresh flowers were stored in amber coloured glass bottles with tight-fitting caps, filled completely with the flowers, for one year at 10°, 28-30°, 37° and 43°. The results of the storage experiments are recorded in Table IV. The values for crude protein, fat, ash and minerals are not shown in the table as there is no change in their percentages which remain the same.

There is no appreciable change in the vitamins of group B. Vitamin-C content dropped from 36.99 mg. to 4.6 mg. at 10° storage, indicating the activity of the ascorbic acid oxidase at 10°. Examination of flowers kept at 28-30°, 37° and 43° did not even show a trace of ascorbic acid. The percentage of total sugar dropped from 89.71 to 63.98. This may be due to the invertase activity which increases with the increase in temperature and time intervals. The invertase activity is greatest at 43°.

DISCUSSION

From Table I it can be observed that vitamin-C is lower than that obtained by Joshi and Magar⁹. They found the vitamin-C content without making use of the formaldehyde technique. Their value (56.0 mg.) corresponds to the total amount of vitamin-C and of reductones which are also present in the mowrah flower extract. In the present case, the formaldehyde technique was employed to obtain the value for vitamin-C only. Patel¹ obtained slightly higher values for thiamin and niacin than the values shown in Table I. These may be due to some conjugates of thiamin and niacin which give the same response to the micro-organisms as the true vitamins.

From Table I it appears that mowrah flowers are a fairly rich source of riboflavin, niacin and ascorbic acid. The amounts of thiamin and folic acid are fairly appreciable. On the whole, these flowers are also a rich source of vitamins and they can be used as a substitute in times of famine and food shortage.

TABLE IV
Effect of storage of mourah flowers at 10°, 28-30°, 37° and 43° for 3, 6, 9 & 12 months.
 (Values for 100 g. of dried flowers)

Constituents.	Before storage.	Mowrah flowers stored (in terms of months)															
		At 10° for				At 28-30° for				At 37° for				At 43° for			
		3.	6.	9.	12.	3.	6.	9.	12.	3.	6.	9.	12.	3.	6.	9.	12.
Moisture (in g.)	21.6	20.80	20.00	19.21	18.97	20.20	19.20	18.30	17.10	14.83	13.38	11.53	10.53	12.69	11.61	11.13	10.03
Reducing sugar (in g.)	66.70	65.94	65.17	64.40	63.63	65.75	63.79	62.33	60.87	66.27	63.83	63.01	60.19	64.42	62.14	59.95	57.57
Total sugar (in g.)	89.71	86.77	83.83	80.89	77.94	85.26	80.81	76.36	71.90	85.10	80.30	71.17	65.03	82.17	74.63	69.35	63.98
Ascorbic Acid (in mg.)	36.99	45.89	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
Thiamin (in µg.)	140.3	140.1	140.0	139.0	138.8	139.9	140.0	139.4	139.0	138.6	136.5	136.1	135.9	138.7	137.0	136.0	135.2
Riboflavin (in µg.)	841.8	841.2	841.4	840.0	839.9	841.0	840.8	840.1	840.0	839.1	838.4	836.4	836.6	839.4	837.7	836.7	836.1
Niacin (in mg.)	1.802	1.800	1.801	1.799	1.799	1.800	1.799	1.799	1.798	1.799	1.799	1.798	1.797	1.801	1.799	1.798	1.797
Folic acid (in µg.)	214.0	213.8	213.3	213.1	213.1	213.7	213.5	213.0	212.8	213.7	213.2	212.9	212.3	213.6	213.2	212.6	211.9

The cause of the destruction of vitamin-C in mowrah flower is definitely due to the presence of ascorbic acid oxidase.

A slightly bitter taste of the flowers and a p_H of 4.0 to 4.5 led to the isolation of malic acid. The coloration with $FeCl_3$ suggested the presence of tannins which were estimated and found to be 1.325%. Both the malic and succinic acids are absent in free form but most of them are in bound form as salts. Free form of acid is present in small amount as can be seen from Table III, from the value of acidity. From the previous communication¹⁵ it can be seen that the mowrah flowers also contain non-protein nitrogen, which led to the investigation about the presence of betaine. The amount of betaine present in the flowers comes to 1.089% which represents about 130 mg. of non-protein nitrogen. The total non-protein nitrogen content is 180 mg. So the difference of 50 mg. may be accounted for by the presence of anthocyanins.

The mowrah flowers gave fermented smell when kept for 3, 6, 9 and 10 months at any temperature. The rate of fermentation varied with the temperature and the period of storage. That is why there is a decrease in the percentage of reducing sugars in all these cases.

S U M M A R Y

1. Thiamin, riboflavin, niacin and vitamin-C were estimated in the mowrah flowers chemically, while folic acid was assayed microbiologically.
2. Ascorbic acid oxidase destroyed 88% of the original vitamin-C present in the mowrah flowers within one month's storage at room temperature (28-30°).
3. The various substances like betaine, tannins, pigments and organic acids (malic and succinic) were analysed and estimated.
4. During storage, there is no change in crude protein, fat, mineral contents and in the vitamins of group B. Vitamin-C, however, is destroyed rapidly. The change in total sugar is due to the invertase activity while the change in reducing sugar is due to auto-fermentation.

R E F E R E N C E S

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